

CHARACTERISTICS OF SLEEP DISORDERS IN PATIENTS WITH
ESSENTIAL ARTERIAL HYPERTENSION

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Annotation

Objective: To study the characteristic features of sleep disorders specific to patients with arterial hypertension.

Material and methods: Research and approaches: As part of our analysis, a main group of 42 participants was formed, including 20 women and 22 men aged 59 to 74 years with established diagnoses of chronic cerebrovascular diseases and hypertension. The control group (CG) consisted of 24 healthy volunteers, including 14 women and 10 men of average age of about 50 years. To assess sleep disorders, both a subjective method - a questionnaire on sleep quality, and objective data from a polysomnographic study were used.

Key words: Hypertension, sleep disorders, Polysomnography, CVD.

Sleep disorders are becoming an increasingly common problem affecting various aspects of health. Insomnia, as one of the most common forms of sleep disorders, in turn, can serve as a precursor to many serious diseases. Studies show that chronic sleep deprivation is associated with an increased risk of developing hypertension, which emphasizes the importance of adequate sleep for maintaining cardiovascular health.

In the context of an increasing trend of sleep disorders, it is important to pay attention to prevention and timely treatment in order to break this vicious circle and improve the overall health of the population. Contacting specialists and

changing your lifestyle can be key steps towards healthy sleep and a better quality of life.

This emphasizes the importance of preventive measures and active blood pressure control. Programs to reduce hypertension and normalize body mass should become a priority in public health. A lifestyle that includes regular physical activity, a balanced diet and giving up bad habits can significantly reduce the risk of cardiovascular diseases. In addition, it is necessary to implement systemic approaches to the treatment of patients with established diagnoses. Effective treatment strategies, including drug therapy and rehabilitation measures, will help prevent the development of acute forms of coronary heart disease and reduce the likelihood of stroke. It is important for patients to be actively involved in their treatment, understand the risks and follow doctors' recommendations.

We must not forget about the importance of regular medical examinations, especially for people with risk factors. Early diagnosis and an individualized approach to each case allow you to notice and correct deviations in time, which will ultimately have a positive effect on the overall mortality rate from cardiovascular diseases.

Conclusion:

Thus, it can be stated that complaints of sleep disorders in patients with chronic cerebrovascular accidents do not correlate with the severity of respiratory disorders during sleep, but reflect the presence of a psychovegetative syndrome characterized by anxiety-depressive manifestations and psychophysiological insomnia. Complex therapy of patients with chronic cerebrovascular accidents should include both the correction of respiratory disorders during sleep and adequate treatment of psychovegetative disorders and anxiety-depressive disorders. A correlation between neurophysiological and psychoemotional changes in dysomnia in patients with hypertension was revealed for the choice of psychocorrection.

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